

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

WP2 – Improving the collection, analysis, and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.7 Report describing core data elements for the collection of pregnancy, immediate child outcomes and longer-term child outcomes in medication exposed pregnancies

Lead contributors	Rebecca Bromley (28 – University of Manchester) Matthew Bluett -Duncan (28 – University of Manchester) Laura Yates (13 – University of KwaZulu-Natal) Yvonne Geissbühler (38 – Novartis) Ian Moore (38 – Novartis) Jonathan Luke Richardson (UK Teratology Information Service) Michael Stellfelt (46 – Novo Nordisk)
Other contributors	N/A

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Abstract

This report summaries the outcomes of three pieces of work from Work Package 2, Task 2.3 which aimed to determine the Core Data Elements required in longer term child health and neurodevelopmental investigations within the ConcePTION Work Package 2 Demonstration Projects.

A systematic literature review and an international Expert Working Group generated evidence and opinion which was then reviewed and discussed within the Task 2.3 Working Group. Core Data Elements including both outcomes and confounder and mediator variables were drafted and added to the previously generated list of Core Data Elements for data collection during pregnancy and in relation to immediate birth outcomes.

This report also provides an updated set of Core Data Elements for the collection of pregnancy related variables and immediate maternal and child outcomes which have been further refined since the last submission.

The described Core Data Elements will be the subject of pilot testing through the Work Package 2 Demonstration Projects. Modifications and amendments will be made following the completion of the Demonstration Projects and will be reported as a final set of recommended Core Data Elements at the end of the project.

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1. Introduction

The Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) ConcePTION Study Work Package 2 aims to improve the direct collection of data in medication exposed pregnancies. Task 2.3 is a set of interrelated sub projects which will create a recommended set of Core Data Elements for use in the ConcePTION Demonstration Projects. In the first submitted report^[1] the results of a review into key regulatory guidelines around the collection of data pertaining to exposed pregnancies and immediate child outcome variables (e.g., congenital anomaly status) was presented. A further review of the data elements used by current major data collection schemes was undertaken and reported. Finally, a series of work has accumulated to produce the first draft of the recommended ConcePTION Work Package 2 Core Data Elements for pregnancy and immediate birth outcome data.

Since the submission of the last report work has continued on the ConcePTION Core Data Elements with regards to the pregnancy and immediate birth outcome data. Additionally, work has been undertaken to develop the recommended common data elements for the collection of longer-term child data including child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes. A systematic literature review, Expert Consensus Delphi Study and Task 2.3 Expert Meetings have all informed the first draft of these Core Data Elements.

An update of the pregnancy and immediate birth outcome core data elements are presented here, whilst a new extension of this set for the follow up of children to document health and neurodevelopmental outcomes is presented. This document remains 'live' and will continue to evolve as we progress through the ConcePTION Work Package 2 Demonstration Projects.

2. Child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes

Certain medications, chemicals and maternal diseases can disrupt processes of human fetal development^[2]. Disruption of normal fetal development trajectories leads to a continuum of outcomes, from those immediately evident such as embryo loss or major physical malformation, through to minor physical deficits. However, there is a range of affects far more diverse than just disruptions to the physical development of the fetus. Less frequently considered, the development of the brain in utero and the functions it is capable of are also susceptible to the effects of a teratogenic exposure^[2, 3]. Effects on the brain range from observable disruptions of structure including cortical development through to functional difficulties with no such visible abnormalities^[2]. Alterations to the development of the neuronal architecture can lead to a myriad of childhood developmental difficulties including delays in early language and motor skill acquisition, lower IQ, poorer educational outcomes and an increased rate of clinical diagnoses such as autism spectrum disorder. Depending on the gestational timing of the exposure, the exposure dose, duration of the exposure and individual susceptibility factors^[4] the neurodevelopmental or neuropsychological impact can range from mild through to substantial and life impacting.

Prescribed medications can have deleterious impacts on human brain development, resulting in mild through to substantial functional difficulties. Anti-convulsant medications such as valproate and phenobarbital impact on fetal brain development, both in human and other mammals^[5] and similarly so do the retinoids^[6]. Fetal exposure to valproate, phenobarbital or isotretinoin produce substantial intellectual deficits, with a characteristic pattern of physical malformations present in only a subset of impaired individuals^[6, 7]. Despite the significance of these teratogen induced neurodevelopmental difficulties, for many exposures there is a mismatch between our knowledge of physical teratogenicity and the potential for neurodevelopmental impact. Largely because many physical abnormalities are present at birth, whereas identification of

neurodevelopmental outcomes requires follow-up of the children concerned. Historically, the physical effects of human teratogens have taken extensive periods, in some cases decades, to determine^[8]; yet for neurodevelopment this is undoubtedly even longer.

Despite recognition of the need to extend medication pharmacovigilance to identify any adverse impact of medications on fetal brain development and the later child neurodevelopmental trajectories, knowing how best to do this remains to be elucidated. To date there is no consensus regarding the key measurable neurodevelopmental outcomes, times of monitoring, the relationship to important exposure variables (e.g., dose) and the significant heterogeneity regarding methodological approaches. There is then the potential to learn valuable lessons from already identified human teratogens and to bring together expertise regarding the investigation of such outcomes to guide future research into new teratogenic influences on neurodevelopment.

Three pieces of work have been undertaken to assist in the creation of the ConcePTION Core Data Elements for longer term child outcomes: 1) a literature review focusing on child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes of reported in already identified human physical teratogens, 2) a Delphi method investigation in to the optimal approaches in the investigation of longer term child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes and 3) the creation of a working set of Core Data Elements to be piloted in the ConcePTION Work Package 2 Demonstration Projects. An executive summary of the outcomes of each of these pieces of work is included below.

3. Human teratogens and longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes: a literature review

Objective: A scoping review was undertaken to systematically identify and extract neurodevelopmental outcome data for medications with established physical teratogenic effects.

Methodology: A list of medications was assembled where there was agreement from teratology experts from within the group that there had been replicated data to demonstrate an association between the medication exposure and a higher risk of abnormal physical developmental outcomes. These medications are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of medications with an association with disruption of structural organ development or growth.

Included medication exposures	
Oral retinoids	Immunosuppressives
Acitretin	Mycophenolate
Alitretinoin	Methotrexate and Aminopterin
Bexarotene	Thalidomide and analogs
Isotretinoin	Thalidomide
Tretinoin	Lenalidomide
Antiepileptic/ anticonvulsants	Miscellaneous
Carbamazepine	Misoprostol
Phenytoin	Diethylstilboestrol
Fosphenytoin	Anticoagulants
Primidone	Coumarin
Topiramate	Phenindione
Valproate	Warfarin
Phenobarbital	Acenocoumarol
Antithyroids	
Carbimazole	
Methimazole	

The search terms were developed in line with PICO guidance which led to the creation of 3 levels: Level 1 determined that the exposure was during pregnancy or when the participant was a fetus; Level 2 outlined the relevant exposures and level 3 the included outcomes. Comparator group was not defined here due to the scoping nature of this review. The search was run through the OVID platform searching both Medline and Embase. The outcome of the searches was validated through the separate searching of the Reprotox database. The search results were reviewed using COVIDENCE Software. Titles and abstracts were independently screened by two authors. Full-text of those identified as potentially relevant were independently screened by two authors to determine final eligibility. Further methodological information is available in the manuscript which is currently being drafted.

Summary of the results:

Over 12,000 abstracts were reviewed to determine eligibility.

The investigation, measurement and reporting of neurodevelopmental outcomes was heterogeneous. With no clear requirements as to the domains required to be investigated or optimal approaches to investigation, where neurodevelopmental investigations had been undertaken, there was substantial variation and diversity in the domains measured and the outcome measures utilized.

Approaches applied to the measurement of neurodevelopmental outcomes ranged from clinical diagnostic instruments to standardized and validated domain-specific assessments and questionnaires, to individual case reports with very little methodological detail. Clinical outcomes measured or reported included diagnosis of intellectual disability, autistic spectrum disorder and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, either at an individual or group level. Domain specific outcomes were typically reported at a cohort level and included

measurements of intellectual, language, memory and attentional skills. Case reports often provided a clinician made judgement on neurodevelopment such as classifying the child as ‘developmentally delayed’ or not, with some references to more specific domains such as speech or motor delay.

Sodium valproate had been the most investigated medication in terms of neurodevelopmental outcomes. Whilst others, despite their association with physical risks had received limited investigation (e.g. mycophenolate, topiramate).

Conclusions: For many of the established physical teratogens there are limited investigations regarding the longer-term child health or neurodevelopmental impact that may be associated with the exposure. A lack of longer-term neurodevelopmental data limits the understanding of a particular medication and the full spectrum of potential risks which may be posed to the developing fetus. This undermines the safe use of medications during pregnancy and potentially places an increased number of children at risk of intellectual, social and behavioral difficulties.

Next Steps: The full review data is currently being written up for publication.

4. Expert consensus group on the assessment of neurodevelopmental outcomes following medication exposures *in utero*.

Objective: The ConcePTION Study strives to improve pregnancy pharmacovigilance. As part of its work, it aims to achieve consensus and to develop systems to improve the collection and reporting of neurodevelopmental outcomes following medication exposures. Expertise within the ConcePTION Consortium was limited for neurodevelopmental outcomes and therefore external experts with experience regarding the effects of exposure to medication or environmental teratogens *in utero* were invited to contribute.

Methodology: Stakeholders (patient, pharmaceutical and regulatory) helped to define longer term follow up topic areas. Members of the expert group were selected based on their research and/or clinical experience within areas of medication, recreational or environmental exposures in utero or during childhood. A Delphi method utilizing three rounds of questions was employed to ascertain expert opinion. Based on the themes identified by the stakeholders, a series of open-ended questions were developed. Responses from Round 1 were collated, additional themes identified, and then additional questions sent round for comment in Round 2 which comprised of questions rated on a 5-point Likert scale. A short summary of the responses given by participants in Round 1 was also provided as feedback for each topic/theme in Round 2. Round 3 was an ‘in person’ virtual meeting held to allow open discussions about yet to reach consensus themes and questions.

Results: 25 experts from 14 countries participated from both clinical and research backgrounds. At the virtual discussion the following topics and narratives pertaining to these themes were developed.

Topic 1. The importance of longer-term neurodevelopmental outcomes in medication exposure research

There was a strong response from all on this question. Neurodevelopment can be susceptible to the deleterious effects of certain exposures and therefore they must be considered with equal importance to congenital anomaly outcomes.

Topic 2. When to prioritize investigation of neurodevelopmental outcomes

There was a broad consensus that the current system of pharmacovigilance is insufficient and that there is a need for routine screening to identify potential risk, as a minimum, and for the development of a purposeful, comprehensive and long-term approach to assessing neurodevelopmental outcomes. However, there

was also a clear narrative that it would be unlikely that routine surveillance for all medications used in pregnancy would be adopted by international regulators. Therefore, opinion was sought as to the criteria which should lead to neurodevelopmental investigations. There was strong support for biological plausibility (e.g., another medication in that class, or central nervous system acting), widely used medications, and physical or neurodevelopmental signals (e.g., from case reports or parent questionnaire's) to lead to expedited, comprehensive investigations. The results of preclinical studies as a signal generator received modest support within the group. There are examples where such data was imperative in the detection of risks (e.g., valproate, isotretinoin) but there was concern from some experts that the signal detection should not simply rely on pre-clinical data. Specifically, there was strong agreement that results from pre-clinical studies alone are not sufficient to reach conclusions about safety or risk. There was strong support for the position that more than one approach should be used to determine which medications are prioritized for investigation.

Topic 3. Core / Central Domains

There was a clear narrative that we should consider neurodevelopmental outcomes as a group of related but independent outcomes. One outcome is not able to be a reliable proxy for another and different impacts on different susceptible neuronal populations may lead to a particular neurodevelopmental endotype. A diagnosis of autistic spectrum disorder for example, will include individuals with alterations in their intellectual ability but there will also be individuals intact intellectual skills. Likewise, individuals with intellectual impairment will include individuals with impaired social functioning but also those who are skilled in their social interactions. An effect on one area of child neurodevelopmental functioning should therefore lead to investigations of the complete endotype.

Experts agreed that parents are particularly interested in “real-life” outcomes and information pertaining to their child’s potential quality of life, and that this should be reflected in outcome/domain selection. Key areas which should be investigated include Cognitive functioning, Neurodevelopmental disorders, Educational outcomes, Social functioning and Behavioral outcomes. Investigations should include broad batteries or outcomes that are developmentally appropriate to ensure optimal identification of teratogenic effects.

It is accepted that one study is unlikely to provide gold-standard data on all outcomes. The group therefore set expectations that investigations across academic, regulatory and industry in their entirety should cover all suggested outcomes with a follow up at least into the adolescent years.

Topic 4. Timing of assessment and the length of follow up

Neurodevelopment is a dynamic variable which sees children’s abilities expanding throughout the child and adolescent years. Language and motor development are the most easily observed and show rapid advancements over time. Therefore, selecting the timepoint for assessment is critical. Too early and the developmental trajectory between children whose development is typical and those whose trajectory is delayed will be not easy to differentiate, unless the difference is severe. There have been cases of teratogenic effects where the level of deviation is detectable in young infants, but the experts noted that children will also grow into deficits. This occurs as the expansion of capabilities in line with chronological age does not occur and the trajectories of development begin to deviate. It is therefore important not to rely solely on the results of an early assessment. Rather, early assessments should ideally be considered alongside later assessments. This approach allows for changes in developmental trajectories over time between exposed and non-exposed children to be properly assessed. Experts were clear that follow ups throughout childhood were

important and clearly stated that conclusions could not be drawn until after investigations have stretched beyond the period of executive functioning development (early twenty's).

It was accepted that investigations should begin in infancy and that there was an ethical requirement here to detect difficulties as soon as possible; to avoid more children being harmed than is necessary to establish risk.

Topic 5. Exposure variables

There was strong consensus that the timing, duration and dose of the exposure are important considerations and analysis should reflect this. It was noted that the neurodevelopmental endotype may vary depending on these factors and this should be considered in investigations.

Topic 6. Confounders and mediator variables

Consensus was reached on key confounders and mediator variables. Those noted to be important included: maternal IQ, socioeconomic status, years in education, age and illness / diagnoses, recreational exposures and other medicine exposures. Child factors which are mediators should optimally include: gender, birth weight, prematurity, infant history of neurological illness and a family history of the outcome in question (e.g., family history of learning disability if the outcomes in question include one or more aspect of cognitive functioning). Although not initially at the level of consensus, following discussion breastfeeding was also agreed to be an important variable to consider as it can be a source of continued exposure and is associated with positive health and neurodevelopmental benefits for the child.

Topic 7. Optimal methodologies

There was strong support for surveillance to be prospective where the mother-child pairs are recruited during pregnancy and followed up longitudinally. This reduces ascertainment bias but is subject to loss to follow-up biases if loss is unbalanced across the groups or driven by a factor related to the exposure. Optimal aspects of investigation included blinded, per protocol assessment of every child in the cohort, which are more attainable in this type of work.

Use of secondary data in pharmacoepidemiology studies has the clear advantage of large populations. But there was consensus that this lacked sensitivity in the measurement of the outcome. The use of these data sets as signal detection methods was strongly supported. However, there was consensus that further investigations would then be required to undertake blinded-assessor investigations, understand the scope of the deficits (e.g., sub diagnosis cases), to look at the extent of impact on other areas of functioning and to collect detailed confounder and mediator data.

It was agreed that secondary use of population data across large cohorts conferred an advantage when screening for possible signals of risk but directly ascertained cohorts where blinded assessments to a specific protocol and with comprehensive assessment and analysis of confounders and mediators were required to draw final conclusions.

Next Steps: The information ascertained from the group has been used in the formation of the recommended Core Data Elements for longer term outcomes. The entire three rounds are being combined into a document which explores these topics in more details. A comprehensive publication on this Delphi-Study has been drafted and will be submitted for publication.

5. Determining Core Data Elements for the ConcePTION project

Objective: To define the Core Data Elements for longer term outcomes required for utilisation within the ConcePTION project Demonstration Projects.

Methodology: The outcomes from the above-described literature review and the Expert Consensus Group were brought into discussions within the Work Package 2, Task 2.3 Working Group. This was a multidisciplinary group who reviewed the results of the above work and looked at how to operationalise information and recommendations into a set of workable Core Data Elements for longer term outcomes within the Demonstration Projects. These were then compared to the already drafted immediate birth outcomes Common Data Elements^[1].

Results: The literature review and Expert Working Group aspects of this project had highlighted that a wider range of neurodevelopmental domains can be altered by in utero exposures. Therefore, the Task 2.3 Working Group determined that the following domains were important for sampling in the demonstration projects: milestone attainments (infants), cognitive, language, motor, social and behavioural functioning. During the discussions of the Expert Group and the ConcePTION Task 2.3 there was a clear message that specific standardised measures should be used where possible to improve the sensitivity of the data. Milestone attainment data in infancy may be used but should be collected prospectively to reduce recall bias.

The recommendation of specific assessment measures is difficult due to complexities including the age of children in the cohort, the neurodevelopmental domain under review, the country in which the data is collected, the expertise of the group and the fact that these are commercial products. Therefore Table 14 includes recommendations regarding key domains of investigation which should be tailored to the individual needs to the specific developmental question, cohort and team.

In Tables 1-14, the specific Core Data Elements for ConcePTION Demonstration Project 3 are presented for the prospective data collection element. For the prospective screening of infant development in Demonstration Project 3 the Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3rd edition [9] has been selected. Its domains and measurement information is displayed in Table 15. Specific item level questions cannot be provided due to copyright. The questionnaire set to be used in the assessment of older children in Demonstration Project 3 and 4 will be developed and piloted as part of the Demonstration Project 3 work.

The Expert Working Group had been clear that entire cohort assessment with face-to-face, blinded assessments to a specific protocol was the gold standard, however this was beyond the financial and time resources of the demonstration projects. Discussions were then had about the expert working group recommendation that a system of screening for signals of neurodevelopmental and child health impact should be developed. Based on this a set of Core Data Elements to be measured via a signal screening approach were developed for the Demonstration Projects. These data elements included both outcomes to be sampled/measured and variables which could be either confounders or mediators for the outcome.

Data elements considered important to the longer term follow up of children exposed to medications in the womb were added to the previously submitted but recently updated ConcePTION Work package 2, Task 2.3 report on Common Data Elements^[1]. The requirements for longer term follow up meant the addition of new common data elements, both pertaining to the collection of longer-term child and neurodevelopmental outcomes but also in terms of background maternal and family factors. For example, parental educational level was not included in the pregnancy and immediate birth outcomes common data elements document but is identified as important here. Similarly, a family history of learning disability or autistic spectrum disorders is imperative for understanding these outcomes but are maybe less important when considering

congenital anomaly outcomes. Thus, the elements required to understand causality can be different for certain longer-term outcomes than for physical immediate outcomes and therefore a bespoke approach to data collection is required, tailored to the outcome in question.

The updated Work Package 2 Core Data Elements are displayed in Appendix Tables 1-13. Whether each element is essential to understanding the longer-term health or neurodevelopmental outcome of children is highlighted.

Next steps: These identified the longer-term Common Data Elements will be utilised in data collection in Work Package 2 Demonstration Project 3 and Demonstration project 4. These recommended points of data collection will be refined as we trial it through these demonstration projects and therefore should be considered to be a 'living document' which will evolve as our experience grows. At the end of the demonstration projects the Core Data Elements will be finalised and submitted as a final report.

6. Conclusions and looking forward

This work is the first to look to identify key Core Data Elements required for longer term outcomes in pregnancies exposed to medications in the womb where direct data collection is being under taken. The work leading up to the creation of the Common Data Elements saw the identification of areas of longer-term health and development which require investigation with the Expert Working Group reviewing and defining best approaches to data collection.

Following refinement of the Common Data Elements, through their piloting in the Demonstration Projects, a final report will be submitted at the end of the project. Standardization of data collection and reporting likely conveys significant benefits and will reduce the latency between a medication's onset of use and knowledge of its neurodevelopmental or neurobehavioral teratogenic impact.

7. References

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8. Appendices

Table 1: Database administrative details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Pregnancy exposure	The report relates to a confirmed pregnancy (where woman was carrying a developing embryo or fetus) with exposure to a medical product	Format: Categorical Values: Y/N	●	○	○	Directly reported	Dataset creation	Only relevant for datasets collecting reports of exposures and clinical outcomes in non-pregnant groups. Would not be needed in pregnancy registries for example, but may be needed in drug registries and spontaneous adverse drug reaction datasets
Mother case identifier	Unique database identifier for the pregnant woman	Alphanumeric	●	●	●	Internally generated	Database functionality Dataset creation	
Baby case identifier	Unique database identifier for each offspring record	Alphanumeric	●	●	●	Internally generated	Database functionality Dataset creation	
Mother-Baby case identifier/link	Common unique identifier linking mother with fetus/fetuses or child/children (same identifier located on both maternal and fetal/offspring records)	Alphanumeric	●	●	●	Internally generated	Database functionality Dataset creation	
Primary reporter type	Type of reporter providing the information	Values: Healthcare professional / Non-healthcare professional	●	●	●	Directly reported	Follow-up/case queries Sub-setting	The primary reporter is assumed to collect information from evolving sources during pregnancy
Primary reporter contact details	Name and contact details for the primary reporter	Primary reporter details	●	●	●	Directly reported	Follow-up/case queries	Contact details may include postal and/or email address and telephone number Availability depends on local law/data collection and storage permissions
Initial report date	Date when pregnancy is initially reported to the data collection system	Initial report date	●	●	●	Directly reported or internally generated	Derivation (Pro-/Retrospective reporting status) Sub-setting	

<p>Prospective status</p>	<p>Prospective - Report of a drug-exposed pregnancy (either during pregnancy or prior to conception) whilst the patient is still pregnant Retrospective - Report of a drug-exposed pregnancy (either during pregnancy or prior to conception) after the pregnancy has ended</p>	<p>Values: Prospective / Retrospective / Unknown</p>	<p>•</p>	<p>•</p>	<p>•</p>	<p>Directly reported Derived (from Initial report date and Date of end of pregnancy)</p>	<p>Where required, alternative definitions of pro-/retrospective can be constructed from the information collected about prenatal tests together with the Initial report date and date of end of pregnancy</p> <p>The collection of additional information is generally recommended to refine the prospective definition (in line with EMA/FDA definitions of pro-/retrospective) to limit the impact of sampling/reporting biases according to the needs of the research activity (important examples include timing of, type of and findings from prenatal screening)</p> <p>Definitions of prospective status are likely to be different for studies investigating longer-term health and neurodevelopmental outcomes</p>
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Table 2: Maternal details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Mother's date of birth	Mother's date of birth	dd/mm/yyyy	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Derivation (age at LMP)	Availability depends on local law/data collection and storage permissions
Mother's age at last menstrual period (LMP)	Mother's age (in years) on the first day of the last menstrual period prior to the pregnancy	Integer	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (Maternal DOB, Date of LMP)	Sub-setting Risk factor	Availability depends on local law/data collection and storage permissions
Household income	The total annual household income (mother and partner before any tax or other deductions).	Value 1: Integer Value 2: Derivation (national population household income in relation to national median - Above / Below / Unknown)	○	◐	•	Directly reported (value 1) Derived (value 2)	Sub-setting Risk factor	An important measure of socioeconomic status Post collection processing to determine if above or below the national average for that country Studies running in a single country with comparable income rates could utilize this as a continuous variable. International studies will require national standardisation
Maternal education	Highest level of education achieved by the mother	Values: 1. No formal education, 2. Primary school (First school/Up to around 11 years), 3. Secondary school (Second school/Up to around 16 years), 4. College (Sixth form/Up to around 18 years), 5. University (18+	○	○	•	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk factor	Post collection processing to determine if above or below the national average for the maternal country

		years)						
Maternal IQ	Intellectual ability of the mother	Values 1: Integer Values 2: Measurement tool (free text)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk factor	Intellectual ability of the mother as measured by a formal, clinically validated tool
Consanguinity	The father of the baby is a first or second degree relative of the mother	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: If yes, detail (free text)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Maternal Height	Height (cm) of the mother at the time of conception	Integer	○	●	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk factor	Convert from feet and inches, etc.
Maternal Weight pre-pregnancy	Actual or approximate weight (kg) of the mother at or around the time of conception	Integer	○	●	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting	Convert from stones and pounds, etc.
Maternal BMI pre-pregnancy	Maternal BMI at the time of conception (kg/m ²)	Integer	●	●	●	Directly reported Derived (Maternal height and maternal weight pre-pregnancy)	Risk factor	
Maternal country	Country in which the mother resides at the time of reporting	NATO codes	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting	
Smoking in pregnancy	Maternal smoking of tobacco during pregnancy	Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y): Details of use (including timing, duration and dose)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Alcohol in pregnancy	Maternal alcohol consumption during pregnancy	Values (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y): Details of use (including timing, duration and dose)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Risk-factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Illicit drugs in pregnancy	Maternal recreational drug use in pregnancy (details of drugs, approximate daily amount ingested, duration of use in pregnancy)	Values (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y): Details of use (including timing, duration and dose)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Folic acid use	Maternal folic acid use in pregnancy	Values 1: None, started pre-conception,	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk-factor	

		started first trimester, started after first trimester Values 2: (If not None): Dose - 400 mcg, 5 mg or other						
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Table 3: Pregnancy details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Date of LMP	Date of the first day of the last menstrual period prior to conception	dd/mm/yyyy	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (EDD)	Derivation (Pro-/retrospective reporting status) Derivation (exposure timing) Derivation (gestational age at pregnancy outcome)	This refers to the LMP associated with this pregnancy (not with earlier cycles) LMP is derived as EDD-280days
Expected date of delivery (EDD)	Expected date of delivery	dd/mm/yyyy	•	•	•	Directly reported	Derivation (Pro-/retrospective reporting status) Derivation (exposure timing) Derivation (gestational age at pregnancy outcome)	The directly reported value may have been based on (e.g.) the date of LMP, results from ultra-sound examinations, the date of embryo transfer (assisted fertilisation). Alternatively, it could be derived in the database from entered dates of LMP based on 280 day gestation length (using the LMP date) or 266 day gestation length (using estimated date of conception from fetal ultrasound measurements)
Source of directly-reported EDD	Clinical calculation of EDD could be based on LMP, Date of embryo transfer (assisted fertilisation), Ultrasound Measurement, or any other obstetric evaluation	Values: LMP / , date of embryo transfer / ultrasound / Other (please detail)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation	The EDD may change over the course of the pregnancy (e.g. those based on date of LMP are potentially inaccurate and can be improved upon by ultrasound measurements performed at the end of the first trimester).
Assisted conception	Assisted conception technique utilised for this pregnancy	Values: (Y/N)	○	○	○	Directly reported	Risk factor	
Plurality	Number of fetuses in current pregnancy	Values: 1, 2, >2	○	•	•	Directly reported	Sub-setting	
Prenatal	Details of any medical prenatal examination	Value 1:	•	•	•	Directly reported	Derivation (Pro-	Values to be reported for each prenatal

test(s)	or test performed to investigate fetal wellbeing/medical conditions	Date test performed Value 2: Approx. gestational age when test performed Value 3: Type of prenatal test (see notes) Value 4: Were any congenital anomalies identified (Y/N) Value 5: Congenital anomaly details/ findings/ diagnosis (free text)					/retrospective status) Derivation (Congenital anomaly status)	test performed Tests to be reported here are only those that have been conducted in a medical setting, social prenatal ultrasound scans should not be described Value 3 example options for tests include: 1. Chorionic Villous Biopsy, 2. Amniocentesis, 3. Cordocentesis, 4. 2d USS, 5. 4d USS, 6. Maternal blood tests, 7. Nuchal translucency, 8. Maternal serum (alpha fetal protein etc.), 9. Other
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Table 4: Maternal medical history details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Maternal pre-pregnancy medical conditions (history)	Maternal medical conditions present prior to pregnancy	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: Diagnosis: MedDRA / ICD10 code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Value 4: Age (in years) at diagnosis (integer)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Demographics table Sub-setting Risk factor	Any pre-existing conditions which may act as risk factors are to be collected. Information may also come from drug indication or concomitant drugs Details regarding maternal mental health are particularly valuable for studies investigating childhood health and neurodevelopmental outcomes, studies investigating these outcomes may benefit from adding separate variables to their data collection forms to ensure this important information is collected

Table 5: Family medical history

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Family history of congenital anomalies	The presence of any congenital anomaly (major or minor) in a sibling, or the mother or the father of the reference pregnancy, or their immediate/ first degree relatives (grandparents, aunts or uncles of the reference pregnancy)	Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y): Details (free text - record details of anomaly, and relationship to the affected family member)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Relevant family history of genetic conditions	The presence of any genetic condition in a relative thought to be the explanation or of relevance to the abnormalities reported in the reference pregnancy.	Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y) : Diagnosis: ICD10 / MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Details (free text - record details of the disorder, and relationship to the affected family member)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Relevant family history of learning disability or of neurodevelopmental disorders	The presence of a learning disability or neurodevelopmental disorder (e.g attention deficit hyperactivity disorder or autistic spectrum disorder) in a sibling, mother, father or their immediate / first degree relatively (grandparents, aunts or uncles of the reference pregnancy)	Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (If Y) : Diagnosis: ICD10 / MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Details (free text - record details of the disorder, and relationship to the affected family member)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic

Relevant family history of health difficulties which onset in childhood	The present of a health condition which onsets in childhood (<18 years of age)	member) Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (if Y) : Diagnosis: ICD10 / MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Details (free text - record details of the disorder, and relationship to the affected family member)	○	○	●	Directly reported	Risk factor	Only the categorical response can be used in data sub-setting or as a risk factor statistic
Number of previous pregnancies	Number of previous pregnancies (including non-live births) experienced by the mother only	Integer	○	○	○	Directly reported	Risk factor	
Number of previous live births	Number of previous live births	Integer	○	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting	
Number of previous spontaneous abortions	Number of previous spontaneous abortions	Integer	○	○	○	Directly reported	Risk factor	
Number of previous induced terminations	Number of previous induced terminations (for any reason)	Integer	○	○	○	Directly reported	Sub-setting	
Number of previous stillbirths	Number of previous stillbirths	Integer	○	○	○	Directly reported	Risk factor	
Previous pregnancies with congenital anomalies	Details of any previous pregnancies which resulted in fetuses/offspring with congenital anomalies (include description of birth defect(s) for each affected fetus/child)	Values 1: (Y/N) Values 2 (if Y): Details (include whether any of these anomalies occurred due to genetic/chromosomal disorders)	○	○	○	Directly reported	Sub-setting	

Table 6: Pregnancy medication exposure details

Each of the following CDE items are to be collected for **each maternal** medication exposure considered relevant to the reported pregnancy (including preconception exposures up to 6 months prior to pregnancy as standard or longer if relevant; e.g. medications with very long half-lives). Multiple start/stop dates should be collected for all medications that are stopped and then restarted.

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous pregnancy outcome reports	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Drug name(s)	International non-proprietary drug name (i.e. active ingredient(s) of the medicinal product)	Value 1: Alphanumeric Value 2: ATC code	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor	Includes the drug(s) targeted for investigation and concomitant drugs
Drug start date	Date at which the medication used during pregnancy was started	dd/mm/yyyy	•	•	•	Directly reported	Derivation (period of exposure: Preconception / Peri-LMP / Trimester 1 / Trimester 2 / Trimester 3) Derivation (gestational age at exposure) Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor	Multiple start/stop dates should be collected for all medications that are stopped and then restarted Start dates are to be recorded for each separate period of use of the drug in the pregnancy under the same record (e.g. Start 1: dd/mm/yyyy, Start 2: dd/mm/yyyy) Missing dates should be entered as “missing”
Drug stop date	Date at which the medication used during pregnancy was stopped	dd/mm/yyyy	•	•	•	Directly reported	Derivation (period of exposure: Preconception / Peri-LMP / Trimester 1 / Trimester 2 /	Stop dates are to be recorded for each separate period of use of the drug in the pregnancy under the same record (e.g. Stop 1: dd/mm/yyyy, Stop 2: dd/mm/yyyy) Missing dates should be entered as “missing”

							Trimester 3) Derivation (gestational age at exposure) Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor	
Drug indication(s)	Specific indication for which the medication was used	Value 1: Free text Value 2: ICD10 / MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: ICD10 / MedDRA	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor	
Peri-LMP exposure	Exposure before LMP in a time period considered relevant to the half-life of the medication under investigation and other concomitant medications (e.g. five half-lives) and/or a time period defined clinically relevant given the expected length of time the medication can produce pharmacodynamics effects	Values: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (Drug start/stop dates, Date of LMP)	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor Statistic / Timing of exposure table	“Exposure” relates to the timing when the medication was administered Possibly easiest to define during data analysis phase using medication start and stop dates
Trimester 1 exposure	Exposure occurring in the first trimester (from date of LMP to LMP+90 days)	Values: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (Drug start/stop dates, Date of LMP/EDD)	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor Statistic / Timing of exposure table	
Trimester 2 exposure	Exposure occurring in the second trimester (from LMP+91 days to LMP+188)	Values: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (Drug start/stop dates, Date of LMP/EDD)	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor Statistic / Timing of exposure table	
Trimester 3 exposure	Exposure occurring in the third trimester (from LMP+189 days onwards)	Values: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (Drug start/stop dates,	Dataset creation Sub-setting/risk factor	

						Date of LMP/EDD)	Statistic / Timing of exposure table	
Route of exposure	Route by which the medication is administered	Values: 1. Aural, 2. Inhalation, 3. Ocular, 4. Oral, 5. IV, 6. IM, 7. Rectal, 8. Topical, 9. Vaginal, 10. Other (please detail)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Sub-setting	
Dose per use	Amount of medication administered per use	Value 1: Unit (g / mg / mcg / IUs etc.) Value 2: Numerical value	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Sub-setting	
Frequency of use	Number of times the medication is taken per unit of time	Value 1: Numeric value (times taken) Value 2: Unit of time (day / 2-days / 3-days / week / 2-weeks / 3-weeks / 4-weeks / month / 2-months / 3-months / 6-months / year / Other (please detail))	•	•	•	Directly reported	Dataset creation Sub-setting	

Table 7: Maternal illnesses and obstetric complication details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Maternal medical conditions arising in pregnancy	Any maternal medical condition arising during pregnancy	alues 1: Detail (free text)Values 2: Diagnosis: ICD10 / MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4 : Gestational age condition diagnosed (days)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Maternal outcomes Table Sub-setting Risk factor	Details regarding maternal mental health are particularly valuable for studies investigating childhood health and neurodevelopmental outcomes, studies investigating these outcomes may benefit from adding separate variables to their data collection forms to ensure this important information is collected
Product/disease-specific maternal outcomes	Maternal outcomes specific to the investigated product, to be decided ad-hoc	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: Diagnosis: free text Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD 9 / ICD10	◐	◐	◐	Directly reported	Statistic / Maternal outcomes Table Sub-setting Risk factor	
Blood group incompatibility	Maternal anti-D antibodies identified in pregnancy	Values: (Y/N)	◐	◐	◐	Directly reported	Risk factor	
Maternal post-partum complications	Any maternal complication occurring post-delivery	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: ICD10/MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10	◐	◐	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Maternal outcomes Table Sub-setting Risk factor	
Maternal death	Death of a woman while pregnant or ≤42 days of the end of the pregnancy (including live/stillbirth delivery, ectopic pregnancy, miscarriage or termination) from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes.	Values 1: Y/N Values 2 (If Y): Date of death dd/mmm/yyyy Values 3 (If Y): Cause of death: MedDRA / ICD10 Value 4: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Maternal outcomes Table Follow-up	

Table 8: Pregnancy outcome details

The following CDE items should be collected for **each fetus** in the reported pregnancy

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Pregnancy outcome collection status	Variable to show whether pregnancy outcome details have been reported to the system	Values: Outcome known / pending / Lost-to-follow-up / missing	○	●	●	Internally generated (derived from reported outcome details)	Dataset creation Follow-up	
Date of end of pregnancy	Date at which the pregnancy completes (for all outcomes).	dd/mm/yyyy	●	●	●	Directly reported Derived (gestational age at end of pregnancy and date of LMP or date of EDD)	Derivation (Pro-/retrospective status) Derivation (LMP/EDD and subsequently exposure timing) Derivation (Gestational age at end of pregnancy)	For live births, this will be the date of delivery (date of birth). For terminations/evacuation of retained products of conception, this will be the date the procedure was performed. For spontaneous abortions or stillbirths, this will be the date when the fetus died if known or estimated from crown rump length (CRL) on autopsy/last ultrasound, last fetal movements, or any other method In cases of fetal demise, the date the death was observed may differ considerably from the date the fetus died
Gestational age at end of pregnancy	Gestational age in days (post-LMP) at the time the pregnancy ended	Integer	●	●	●	Directly reported Derived (date of end of pregnancy and date of LMP or date of EDD)	Derivation (Pro-/retrospective status) Derivation (LMP/EDD and subsequently exposure timing) Derivation (Timing of live	Calculated as either the time since the first day of the LMP or from prenatal ultrasound scans If necessary, converted from Weeks and days (post-LMP) or Weeks and days (based on prenatal ultrasound measurements)

							birth) Derivation (SGA)	
Induced termination	Induced abortion (either medical or surgical) of a pregnancy for any reason	Values 1: Y/N Values 2 (If Yes) Reason for termination: - 1. Non-medical reason, - 2. Medical reason (maternal indication) - 3. Medical reason (fetal indication) - 4. Other (please detail), - 5. Unknown	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Collection of the specific indications is not in scope for the ConcePTION project
Ectopic pregnancy	Implantation outside of the endometrial cavity (including tubal, cervical, caesarean scar, interstitial, cornual, ovarian, abdominal, heterotopic or of unknown location) confirmed by transvaginal ultrasound.	Values: Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Stillbirth	Death of a fetus prior to the complete expulsion or extraction from its mother, after the 22nd completed week post-LMP (≥ 154 days) of pregnancy; the death is indicated by the fact that after such separation the fetus does not breathe or show any other evidence of life, such as beating of the heart, pulsation of the umbilical cord or definite movement of voluntary muscles	Values: Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	In line with EMA recommendations, stillbirth is defined as fetal loss >22 completed weeks post-LMP for the purposes of the ConcePTION project International definitions of stillbirth vary. Some definitions rely purely on the gestational age at pregnancy loss (varying from 20 weeks post-LMP to 28 weeks post-LMP), others also consider the weight of the fetus at pregnancy loss (e.g. fetal weight $>500g$ required to classify as a stillbirth/intrauterine death)
Spontaneous abortion	Death of a fetus prior to the complete expulsion or extraction from its mother, before the 22nd completed week of	Values: Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	See above

	pregnancy (≤ 153 days).							
Molar pregnancy	A non-viable product of conception which can be either a 'complete mole' arising after single sperm fertilisation of an ovum lacking genetic material, or a 'partial mole' which arises as a consequence of multi-sperm fertilisation of a healthy ovum. An invasive mole (formerly known as chorioadenoma destruens) is a hydatidiform mole that has grown into the muscle layer of the uterus	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: (if YES): - Hydatidiform Mole (complete or partial) / - Invasive Mole - Mole of Unknown Type	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Blighted ovum	A non-viable pregnancy in which the embryo either never develops, or begins to develop and is reabsorbed. Diagnosis requires ultrasound examination to establish a gestational sac diameter of >25 mm with no fetal pole detected	Values: Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Live birth	Delivery of a fetus, irrespective of the duration of the pregnancy, which after separation shows signs of life, such as beating of the heart, breathing, pulsation of the umbilical cord, or definite movement of voluntary muscles	Values: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	

Table 9: Delivery details

The following CDE items should be collected for **each delivery event** in the reported pregnancy (e.g. in rare cases where there is more than one delivery event at different times or where delivery methods vary for each fetus/infant)

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Labour onset	How labour began	Values: Natural onset / membrane sweep / amniotomy / vaginal prostaglandin tablet, pessary or gel / mifepristone / misoprostol / other (please detail)	◐	○	○	Directly reported	Sub-setting / Risk factor	
Mode of delivery	The method by which the fetus was delivered from the mother	Values: Spontaneous vaginal delivery (incl. vertex/breach) / Assisted vaginal delivery (incl. forceps / ventouse) / Emergency C-section (post-labour / pre-labour) / Elective C-section	◐	○	◐	Directly reported	Sub-setting / Risk factor	
Maternal delivery complications	Any maternal complications arising as a result of the delivery method during or after delivery	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: Diagnosis: MedDRA / ICD10	◐	○	●	Directly reported	Sub-setting / Risk factor	

		Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Timing of complication details (free text)							
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Table 10: Live/stillborn birth outcome details

The following CDE items should be collected for **each live or stillborn infant** from the reported pregnancy

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Gestational timing of live/stillborn offspring	Whether a live birth or stillbirth was preterm, term, or post-term infant	Values: Pre-term / full term / post-term	•	•	•	Directly reported Derived (gestational age at end of pregnancy) Derived (date of end of pregnancy and date of LMP or date of EDD)	Statistic / Outcomes table	The directly reported value may be based on the date of LMP or on assessments from prenatal ultrasound scans Preterm is <37 weeks (<259 days), full-term is ≥37 to <42 weeks (≥259 and <294 days), and post-term is ≥42 weeks (≥294 days)
Infant birth weight	Weight of the offspring at delivery	Integer (in grams)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table Derivation (SGA and LGA)	
Infant sex	Sex of the offspring at birth	Values: Male / Female / Undetermined / Unknown	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table Derivation (SGA and LGA)	
Infant head circumference	Occipito-frontal circumference (i.e. the widest circumference of the skull from the broadest part of the forehead (above the eyebrow and ears) to the most prominent part of the rear of the head), measured using a non-stretchable flexible tape - to be recorded in cms	Integer (in centimeters)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table	
Infant birth length	Heel to crown (knees flat) measurement of recumbent infant length - to be recorded in cms	Integer (in centimeters)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table	
Small for Gestational Age at	An infant born with a birth weight less than the 10th centile on population-level	Values Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table	

delivery	infant birth weight charts (these may be customised for various factors including gestational age at delivery as a minimum and additionally maternal BMI, parity and ethnicity, and infant sex).							
Large for Gestational Age at Delivery	An infant born with a birth weight greater than the 90th centile on population-level infant birth weight charts (these may be customised for various factors including gestational age at delivery as a minimum and additionally maternal BMI, parity and ethnicity, and infant sex)	Values Y/N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table	
Apgar score	Apgar score at set time intervals post-delivery	<p>1-Min Score Value 1: Known / Unknown Value 2 (If Known): Integer (0-10)</p> <p>5-Min Score Value 1: Known / Unknown Value 2 (If Known): Integer (0-10)</p> <p>10-Min Score Value 1: Known / Unknown Value 2 (If Known): Integer (0-10)</p> <p>15-Min Score Value 1: Known / Unknown Value 2 (If</p>	○	○	○	Directly reported	Statistic / Infant details table	Apgar is a clinical scoring system used to establish the clinical status of the newborn at one and five minutes post-delivery, and every additional five minutes until 20 minutes in infants with ongoing Apgar scores <7. The scoring system comprises five components investigating: Appearance (skin colour), Pulse (heart rate), Grimace (reflexes), Activity (muscle tone) and Respiration (respiration rate). Scores of between 0 and 2 are provided for each component depending on the clinical features of the newborn, providing summary scores of between 0 and 10. Scores of 7-10 are reassuring, 4-6 moderately abnormal, and 0-3 as low

		Known): Integer (0-10) 20-Min Score Value 1: Known / Unknown Value 2 (If Known): Integer (0-10)						
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Table 11: Live born neonatal/infant outcome details

The following CDE items should be collected for each **live born infant** from the reported pregnancy

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Neo-natal complications	Any complication experienced in the neonatal period (from birth until 28 completed days of life)	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: Diagnosis: MedDRA / ICD 10 / Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Age at diagnosis in days (integer)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Postnatal death of live born infant	Details of the death of a live born infant	Values: Yes/No Values 2 (If Yes):	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table Follow-up	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Neonatal death (Age at death: up to 28 completed days), - Infant death after the neonatal period (Age at death: >28 completed days) - Child death (Age at death: >1 year) Values 3 (If Yes): Date of death (dd/mm/yyyy)						
Age at death of neonate/infant / child	Age of the child on the day of death	Values 1: Integer Values 2: Unit (days, weeks, months, years)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table Follow-up	Record age at death in days for children <1 month old, record in months for children <2 years old and years in children ≥2 years
Product/disease-specific outcomes	Offspring outcomes specific to the investigated medicinal product	Values 1: Y/N Values 2: Diagnosis: ICD10/MedDRA code Value 3: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 4: Age at diagnosis details (integer)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table Follow-up	Examples may include measures of immune function in the offspring of those exposed to immunosuppressant <i>in utero</i>

Table 12: Malformation details

The following CDE items should be completed for **each fetus** in the reported pregnancy

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Congenital anomaly	Any structural/morphological, functional or biochemical anomaly(ies) in the fetus that occur during intrauterine life and can be identified prenatally, at birth or later in life	Values 1: Y / N	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Details of all congenital anomaly(ies)	Details of the anomaly(ies) present in the exposed fetus	Value 1: Diagnosis: free text in accordance with coded diagnostic term(s) Value 2: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10 Values 3: Age at diagnosis details (free text)	•	•	•	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table Sub-setting	These fields will be empty where no anomalies are described It is important to confirm the details through postnatal examination / investigation or post mortem Record details for each anomaly separately
Infant malformation case classification	Classification of status of a fetus / infant case with an anomaly(ies) based on a hierarchy of observed events	Value 1: Does the baby have any structural malformation events or birth defects (i.e. non-functional/biochemical anomalies)? - Y / N	•	•	•	Derived (from Details of the congenital anomaly(ies) variable)	Statistic / Outcomes table Sub-setting	Each congenital malformation event is judged by experienced adjudicators (qualified paediatrician, clinical geneticist, teratologist, paediatric neurologist, nephrologist, toxicologist, or clinical pharmacologist), according to the

		<p>Value 2: (if yes) Are there any genetic/cytogenetic malformation events?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Y (classify case as genetic malformation case) - N (classify case per EUROCAT) as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Major malformation case - NOS malformation case - Minor malformation case 					<p>EUROCAT guidance</p> <p>In fetuses/infants with more than one malformation, the case categorisation is determined by the presence of any anomaly meeting the criteria of the highest-ranking category in the following hierarchy: Major malformation > Unspecified malformation (“NOS”; not otherwise specified) > Minor malformation</p> <p>Please refer to the decision aid in the appendix to assist the classification of anomalies/malformations</p>
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Table 13: Longer-term child health outcome details

It is recognised that not all child longer-term outcomes will be able to be covered by a single study but the domains listed here should be covered by a set of complementary studies, which together build up a comprehensive evidence-base

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Child medical problems	Has the child had any medical problems since birth.	Multiple Choice Values: Y/N	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Not a static status. To be collected at intervals throughout childhood.
Child medical problems - details	Description of child's medical problems.	Values: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Display if Health problem is present
Child specialist visit	Has the child required any specialist reviews?	Multiple choice values: Paediatrician, Nutritionist, Clinical Geneticist, Ophthalmologist, Child Development Centre, Audiologist, Physiotherapist, Speech Therapist, Occupational Therapist, Psychologist, Other	●	●	●		Statistic / Outcomes table	Not a static status. To be collected at intervals throughout childhood.
Child medication	Child chronic medication use.	Value 1: Alphanumeric Value 2: ATC code	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Not a static status. To be collected at intervals throughout childhood.
Child professional concerns	Report of any developmental concerns raised by professionals.	Multiple Choice Values: Y/N	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Not a static status. To be collected at intervals throughout childhood. Maybe educational or health professional who raises concerns.
Child professional concerns – details	Description of developmental concerns raised by	Free text	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes	

	professionals.						table	
Child vision difficulties	Difficulties with child vision.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have these been confirmed by an eye test?	◦	◦	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child vision difficulties - details	Description of vision problems.	Values: Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◦	◦	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child hearing difficulties	Difficulties with child hearing.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have these been confirmed by a hearing test? Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◦	◦	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child toileting difficulties	Does the child have any frequent difficulties with the passing of urine or opening of their bowels?	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have there been any investigations. Free text response. Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◦	◦	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child eczema/ skin conditions	Diagnosis of eczema or other skin conditions.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have there been any investigations. Free text response.	◦	◦	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	

		Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text						
Child asthma/ respiratory conditions	Diagnosis of asthma or other respiratory conditions.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have there been any investigations. Free text response. Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◐	◐	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child congenital heart disease	Diagnosis of congenital heart disease.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have there been any investigations. Free text response. Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◐	◐	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	
Child food allergies	Diagnosis of food allergies.	Value 1: Y/N Value 2: (if yes) have there been any investigations. Free text response. Value 3: (if yes) Coding system: MedDRA / ICD10; free text	◐	◐	●	Directly Reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	

Table 14: Longer-term child neurodevelopmental outcome details

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Essential to attempt collection of:			Source	Purpose	Notes
			Spontaneous or adverse event reporting	Outcomes in pregnancy and infant first year	Longer term outcomes			
Child Cognitive Functioning	The expected developmental level within the area of cognitive functioning varies by the age of the child. This should be measured via age appropriate assessment using either 1. parental completed questionnaires 2. through direct research / clinical assessment of the child or 3. Diagnoses of deficits (e.g. intellectual disability). 4. Attainment of key milestones.	Will depend on the method of collection	○	○	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Includes functioning in the areas of intelligence, memory, attention and executive functioning. Attainment of cognitive milestones can be used but due to normal variation in attainment times and cross-cultural differences, standardized questionnaire or assessments are more valid.
Child Motor Functioning	The expected developmental level within the area of motor functioning varies by the age of the child. This should be measured via age appropriate assessment using either 1. parental completed questionnaires 2. through direct researcher assessment of the child or 3. Diagnoses of deficits relating to motor development/ functioning (e.g. dyspraxia). 4. Attainment of key milestones.	Will depend on the method of collection	○	○	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Includes functioning in the domains of fine and gross motor development and hand-eye co ordination. Attainment of motor milestones can be used but due to normal variation in attainment times and cross-cultural differences, standardized questionnaire or assessments can be more valid.
Child Language Functioning	The expected developmental level within the area of language functioning varies by the age of the child. This should be measured via age appropriate assessment using either 1. parental completed	Will depend on the method of collection	○	○	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Includes expressive, receptive, pragmatic, semantic and oromotor production. Attainment of language milestones can be used

	questionnaires 2. through direct research / clinical assessment of the child or 3. Diagnoses of deficits (e.g. intellectual disability). 4. Attainment of key milestones.							but due to normal variation in attainment times and cross-cultural differences, standardized questionnaire or assessments can be more valid.
Child Social Functioning	The expected level of social functioning varies by the age of the child. This should be measured via age appropriate assessment using either 1. parental completed questionnaires 2. though direct researcher assessment of the child or 3. Diagnoses of deficits relating to motor development/ functioning (e.g. dyspraxia). 4. Attainment of key milestones.	Will depend on the method of collection	●	●	●	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Includes review of early and later social competence. Attainment of social milestones can be used but due to normal variation in attainment times and cross-cultural differences, standardized questionnaire or assessments can be more valid.

Table 15: Neurodevelopmental and child health data to be collected as part of the Demonstration 3 prospective study at 6 and 12 months of age.

Data variable	Definition	Recommended data format and suggested values	Measurement	Source	Purpose	Notes
Communication_Score	6 questions relating to receptive and expressive infant language development.	Value: 'on time' vs 'at risk'	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition- Communication	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers
Fine Motor_Score	6 questions relating to infant finer motor development.	Value: 'on time' vs 'at risk'	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition- Fine Motor	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers
Gross Motor_Score	6 question relating to larger motor movement development.	Value: 'on time' vs 'at risk'	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition – Gross Motor	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers
Problem Solving_Score	6 questions relating to early cognitive skills.	Value: 'on time' vs 'at risk'	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers
Personal and Social_Score	6 questions relating to infant social development.	Value: 'on time' vs 'at risk'	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers
Child Health_questions	Open ended question regarding	Free Text	Ages and Stages Questionnaire,	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes	Available under Licence

	chronic health conditions.		3 rd Edition		table	from Brookes Publishers
Child Vision and hearing	Open ended questions regarding the child's hearing and vision.	Free Text	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, 3 rd Edition	Directly reported	Statistic / Outcomes table	Available under Licence from Brookes Publishers

